

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14416998

Implementation of Semi-Immersive Virtual Reality in Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management Towards Enhancing Students' Learning Experiences and Soft Skills

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ABSTRACT

Virtual reality (VR) is a promising tool that can improve learning and skills in higher education with potential to convert the way we learn and teach, from providing in-depth knowledge and assisting us comprehend composite subjects to simplifying language immersion and virtual trips. Semi-Immersive virtual environments provide chances to enhance courses with experiential and realistic learning experiences. As modern advancements of technological possibilities advance speedily, more and more researchers report on adopting virtual reality for learning – albeit such work often has a more or less experimental character. However, virtual reality base of knowledge in higher education is growing rapidly; educators who want to engage learning using virtual reality to amend courses, to extend the syllabus with experiential learning, or who want to offer new content enabled through virtual reality, find increasingly rich advice. The research work deliberates on the relevance and competences of implementing Semi-Immersive Virtual Reality System using SimLab VR Simulator in Katsina State Institute of Technology and management (KSITM) with benefits of enhancing Learning through experience, allowing Students to bring 3D objects to life and makes visualization a reality, enabling the experience of real scenarios or fabricated experiences over and over, and learn in an immersive way. The Objectives include Semi-Immersive Virtual reality implementation, bringing learning experience to life, improved group and collaborative learning, prepare Students for workspace and jobs thereby enabling students' recruitment. Potential challenges in implementing semi-immersive VR at KSITM were identified and strategies to overcome them were suggested. The anticipated result is a shift into an experienced learning which will enable students to be able to build their real-world skills and employability.

Keywords: virtual reality, experimental learning, 3D-objects, visualization and collaborative learning.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Virtual Reality (VR) technology has significantly impact a lot of benefits in Higher educational sector, shaping how Students learn with course material. Interaction with simulated environments enable Students to learn based on immersive experience. The systems of virtual Reality can

vary from fully immersive setups, which include headsets and motion-sensing technology, to semi-immersive systems, which are reliant on Visual screens and partly interactive components are less expensive. Although fully immersive VR can be more engaging, semi-immersive VR provide an accessible substitute that can still raise an improved learning experience without the high prices. The Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management (KSITM) has been among the lead institutions of technical education in Northern Region, training Students with Skills in arenas such as information technology, engineering and management. Nevertheless, the old-style teaching methods presently used may limit students' capability to fully grasp and apply practical skills essential in today's workforce. Moreover, many places of jobs are now looking for strong soft skills graduates- such as collaboration, problem-solving and communication-yet these talents are often challenging to foster in an old-styled or traditional based classroom setup. Semi-immersive VR could address these challenges by creating a more interactive and engaging learning environment. By simulating real-world tasks and encouraging collaborative work, VR can not only improve understanding of course material but also help students develop critical soft skills. This study aims to explore the implementation of semi-immersive VR at KSITM and assess its potential impact on students' learning experiences and skill development.

Virtual reality (VR) encompasses hardware and software systems that pursue to perfect an all-inclusive, sensual illusion of being present in another atmosphere or Environment. In relation to other information systems, VR allows a mainly high level of immersion, existence and interactivity (Mutterlein, 2018). Based on these characteristics, VR promises to be a tool that can enhance higher education (Wohlgenannt et al 2020). The hardware and tools used in creating virtual environments have been enhanced profoundly. However, recent applications of VR in higher education often have an experimental personality (Radianti, 2020). It is predominantly beneficial for experiential learning, which can improve Students learning success (Fromm et. Al 2021). Immersive virtual environments can offer rich experiences and thereby add value to courses, allowing students to acquire knowledge in an individual way. In recent years, there have been rapid development in VR technologies. Among the first uses of VR in higher education was to train students' soft skills. Virtual Speech is being used by universities around the world to enhance communication skills useful for employment after graduation. The implementation of VR technology in higher education signifies a substantial shift in academic practices, targeting to handle the growing needs and potentials of today's learners. With its capability to build immersive and interactive learning experiences (Li et. Al 2023), VR has the potential to enhance student commitment, raise deeper understanding of composite ideas, and eventually progress learning results (Parmar et. Al 2022). However, as the assurance of VR is enticing education, a complete comprehension of its influence on students' learning experiences is still in the nascent stages of exploration (Li et. Al 2023).

The educational prospective of VR lies in its ability to transport students to virtual worlds, providing experiential learning environments that are not confined by the physical limitations of a traditional classroom. Computers, headsets, VR simulators and mobile phones are main devices for VR application in the field higher Education and used in this research. The main equipment for VR applications are Computers through which virtual laboratories can be made. The VR head-mounted device have a future known as Head-mounted display device which block user's vision hearing of the surrounding/external environment, and make user to have feeling of being in the virtual environment which bring an excellent real experience so that book content appears interactive and perceptible (Ding and Li, 2022). There are Five innovative types of VR Systems such as Non-immersive, Fully Immersive, Semi-immersive, Augmented Reality and Collaborative VR. Semi-immersive VR system, allow users to perceive both the virtual environment and real world to see themselves either through a screen or VR box/headset in the virtual world thereby having contact with the real world (Keersmaeker et. Al 2024). This research work centers on the implementation of semi-immersive VR System in Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management being most cost-effective VR which help teachers ultimately presents lectures more engagingly and realistically instead of sticking on theoretical descriptions only.

Statement of the problem

The traditional lecture-based teaching methods used at the Katsina State Institute of Technology and Management may fall short in engaging students or adequately preparing them for practical, real-world challenges. Students often struggle with understanding complex concepts without hands-on, interactive learning experiences. Furthermore, soft skills—such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving—are increasingly critical for employability but are difficult to develop within conventional academic settings. VR offers a promising solution to these issues. However, fully immersive VR setups are expensive, often making them impractical for institutions with limited resources. Semi-immersive VR, which can be implemented at a fraction of the cost, could provide similar benefits by engaging students in interactive simulations and virtual environments. Despite its potential, there is limited research on the use of semi-immersive VR at institutions like KSITM and its effectiveness in enhancing learning and soft skills. Therefore, this study seeks to evaluate the implementation of semi-immersive VR at KSITM, exploring its impact on both academic understanding and the development of essential soft skills. The following problems are associated with Traditional teaching instruction which affects the quality and standard of education leading to the urgent need of implementing a VR education System in KSITM as follows:

1. **One-size-fits-approach:** Traditional teaching instruction is associated with one-time-fits-approach as a result of its inability to provide Students with personalized learning experience. Regardless of Students interest they are forced to follow same learning style, this what make Students too oftentimes find traditional education uninteresting and boring.
2. **Non-availability of Skill-based Education:** Another obstacle of traditional teaching delivery is lack of skill-based and creative education. Innovation, creative thinking, flexibility and practicality are the demands of almost all kinds of professions in this digitized modern world.
3. **Teacher-centered learning:** The main source of information are Teacher and books. Students will not be able to learn new things, and the acquisition of knowledge depends only on Techers and books.
4. **Lack of Immersion:** Traditional Style of teaching lacks immersion which makes learning experience more interactive, captivating and memorable for Students.
5. **Collaboration and social interaction:** Students lack ability of interaction with each other in the same virtual space to work together on projects, problem solving or engagement in discussions to foster teamwork and social interactions.

So, these were a handful of problems associated with traditional teaching approach. These are the major reasons why an efficient and advanced VR learning environment has become a desire need for KSITM being among technology based Institutions to cope-up with existing real and experienced World.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of implementing semi-immersive Virtual reality in KSITM is to enhance Students' learning experiences and develop their soft skills by providing interactive, engaging, and realistic virtual environments. The research objectives are stated as follows:

1. To assess the current state of the learning environment at KSITM and identify challenges related to student engagement and soft skill development.
2. To examine the effectiveness of semi-immersive VR in improving students' comprehension of complex concepts.
3. To evaluate how VR-based simulations can foster the development of soft skills, including teamwork, communication, and problem-solving.
4. To identify potential challenges in implementing semi-immersive VR at KSITM and suggest strategies to overcome them.

Research questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the current limitations of traditional teaching methods at KSITM in terms of engaging students and developing soft skills?
2. How does semi-immersive VR impact students' engagement and understanding of complex topics?
3. What specific soft skills can be developed through the use of semi-immersive VR simulations?
4. What obstacles might KSITM face in implementing semi-immersive VR, and how can these challenges be addressed?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance were formulated to further guide the study:

1. The implementation of semi-immersive Virtual reality does not significantly improve Students' learning experiences or soft skills at KSITM.
2. There is no significant improvement in Students' engagement and comprehension when semi-immersive VR is used.
3. Students and lecturers do not perceive semi-immersive VR as an effective tool for learning and skill development.
4. Semi-immersive virtual reality does not lead to significant improvement in students' soft skills, such as communication, teamwork, or problem solving.

Review of Related literature

a. Introduction to Virtual Reality in Education

Virtual reality (VR) uses hardware and software systems to create a realistic experience that does not exist in reality which seek to perfect an all-inclusive, sensory illusion of being present in another environment. In relation to other information systems, VR enables a particularly high level of immersion, presence and interactivity (Mutterlein, 2018). Virtual Reality (VR) has emerged as a transformative technology in education, offering immersive and interactive learning experiences. Semi-immersive VR, which uses tools such as desktop VR, large screens, or projectors, bridges the gap between traditional learning and fully immersive VR by providing a balance of cost-effectiveness and functionality. It enables students to interact with simulated environments while maintaining a connection to the real world, making it ideal for resource-limited institutions like KSITM.

b. Technological shift of higher Education

The incorporation of technology in the continually-evolving landscape of higher education has become vital (Raj et. Al 2023). The digitized revolution resulted to the implementation of numerous technologies in pedagogy, renovating the way students access, engage and interact with educational content. In this transformative trip, offering exciting possibilities for reshaping old-style classroom experiences, VR technology has arisen as a frontrunner. Virtual Reality, as a computer-generated simulation of a 3D environment, holds vast assurance in education (Kuna et. Al 2023). It lets students to interact with and explore complex subjects in immersive, interactive and experienced environments. By exceeding the limitations of physical classrooms, VR provides experiential learning opportunities that can meaningfully influence educational results. Virtual reality (VR) uses hardware and software systems to create a realistic experience that does not exist in reality which seek to perfect an all-inclusive, sensory illusion of being present in another environment. In relation to other information systems, VR enables a particularly high level of immersion, presence and interactivity (Mutterlein, 2018).

c. Improving Student engagement/commitment

Student engagement is one of the most exciting features of VR technology (Tsirulnikov et Al 2023). Old-fashioned lectures and textbooks can sometimes fight to captivate the concentration of students, leading to reduced learning engagement. VR, however, has the capability to captivate learners through its immersive experiences. It influences active learning, where students actively take part in their education. This results to improved motivation, involvement, and a profounder connection with the subject matter experience. By

means of VR education, educators can be able to build self-motivated, multisensory learning experiences that cater to diverse learning styles. By appealing to visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners, VR can facilitate deeper understanding and retention of complex concepts (Obukhov et, Al 2023).

d. Influence on learning outcomes

The effect of VR on learning outcomes is another precarious area of exploration. Preliminary studies suggest that, Increased knowledge acquirement and retention resulted from integration of VR technology which leads to improved learning outcomes (Buttussi and Chittaro, 2023). The capability of VR to provide practical, experiential learning opportunities is particularly advantageous for subjects that traditionally depends on theoretical instruction. Furthermore, VR provide the prospective for personalized learning involvements. Adaptive VR settings can alter content and striving levels to individual student needs, catering to the diverse abilities and prior knowledge of learners. This adaptability holds the potential of more efficient and effective learning experience (Sucke et. Al 2023).

The idea/concept of virtual reality in education

Virtual reality technology can improve the learning experience. It enables learners to gain knowledge in a hands-on or practical process. Semi-Immersive virtual reality, supported by hardware devices, surrounds the human senses of sight, hearing, and touch, significantly improving the immersion experience for the learner students feel and experience how cybersecurity has been presented in a virtual world. The VR experiment thereby served a twofold purpose as experiment and learning experience. As a side effect, this provided a realistic setting for the experiment (Majchrzak, 2022); in addition, immersive virtual reality systems that support multiplayer interaction are commonly used in architectural design to enhance learners' spatial perception and experience. virtual reality can be used to design 3D interactive virtual animation scenes for students to learn visualization of teaching content in a realistic environment, and virtual reality can be used to create visual models or simulators to deepen learners' understanding of learning content.

Figure 1: Virtual Reality Concept diagram (Xiaoting Wang, 2023)

Benefits of virtual reality in higher education

Thompson, 2023 Stated benefits of VR in Higher education as follows:

Enhancing learning and soft skills: A significant benefit of using VR in education is that Students learn based-on experience. In VR We can bring 2D objects to life and makes visualization a reality, allowing us to experience real scenarios or fabricated experiences over and over, and learn in an intelligent way.

1. For distance learning: A big factor concerning VR is helping to promote distance learning. As Institutes campuses become global, the location independence of VR becomes more prominent.
2. To bring learning to life: One of the most obvious benefits of VR is transforming lectures into experienced learning experiences, enabling lecturers to truly bring their subject to life.

3. Prepare students for the workplace and jobs: Practical uses of VR in higher education is opening VR labs and is a significant stage in encouraging content development and setting a global standard for VR content.
4. For student recruitment: One of the Competitive business is Recruiting students, campus tours are an essential part of the process. Not only can it become expensive for the prospective student, it's also time-consuming for them and their families.

Semi-Immersive Virtual Reality

Combination of non-immersive and fully immersive virtual reality is known as Semi-immersive virtual reality. This VR System can be implemented using SimLab VR Studio which is a complete VR creation tool capable of building specialized interactive VR experiences for high quality 3D Visualization. SimLab can transform higher education experience, where you can unleash Students creativity and bring any design to life, from Computers, engineering to wide variety of disciplines (Son et. Al, 2024). Students can move about on their own which can be in the form of a 3D space or virtual environment, either through a computer screen or a VR box/headset. So all activities within the virtual world are focused toward Students. However, Students have no real physical movements other than their visual experience. On a computer, the lecturer can use the mouse to move about the virtual space, and on mobile devices, based on touch and swipe to move about the place. Semi-immersive virtual environments support Gyroscope, which means the virtual space will be fixed on mobile phone based on the vertical axis, and then to literally move the phone about in different directions to view the virtual environment in those directions. The Students that are connected to VR boxes are more interactive since they are also a form of Gyroscope, but without lecturer using His hands.

Figure 2: VR box/headset (Marchionne, F. 2019).

Figure 3: Semi-immersive Virtual Reality LAB (Son et. Al, 2024)

METHODOLOGY

Research design

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques. The primary reason for choosing a mixed-methods approach is to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the impact of semi-immersive VR on student learning experiences and soft skills. Quantitative data, collected through surveys and performance tests, will provide measurable evidence of VR's effectiveness, while qualitative data, gathered through interviews and observations, will offer insights into students' subjective experiences and perceptions. Specifically, an experimental design will be used to measure learning outcomes and soft skills development before and after the VR intervention. A control group, following the traditional teaching method, will be compared to the experimental group, which will use semi-immersive VR to engage with course material. This design allows for a controlled comparison of traditional and VR-based instruction, providing reliable data on VR's impact.

Population of the study

The study population includes students from selected departments at KSITM, particularly those enrolled in courses where hands-on, interactive learning is essential, such as information technology and engineering. The choice of these departments is based on their suitability for VR applications and the practical skills required in these fields. The study will focus on students in their second year, as they have foundational knowledge of their subjects and are likely to benefit most from VR-enhanced learning experiences. School members involved in teaching these students may also be included to gather feedback on VR's impact on their instructional practices.

Sample and sampling technique

Sampling Technique: A stratified random sampling technique will be used to select participants, ensuring representation across different departments and academic years. This approach helps maintain diversity within the sample and ensures that the results are reflective of the entire student body in relevant fields.

Sample Size: A sample of approximately 80 students will be selected, with 40 students assigned to the experimental group (using semi-immersive VR) and 40 to the control group (traditional learning methods). School members who teach these courses will also be invited for interviews to provide insights on VR's effectiveness from an instructional perspective.

Research Instruments

To collect both quantitative and qualitative data, several research instruments will be employed:

1. **Questionnaires:** Pre- and post-intervention questionnaires will be administered to assess students' knowledge of course material, engagement, and self-assessment of soft skills (communication, teamwork, problem-solving).
2. **Performance Tests:** Tests will be designed to objectively measure students' understanding of course content before and after the intervention. The tests will cover topics relevant to the VR simulations and traditional lessons.
3. **Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with a subset of students from both the experimental and control groups, as well as School members. The interviews will explore students' and teachers' experiences, perceptions of VR, and feedback on its effectiveness.
4. **Observation Checklists:** Observational data will be collected during the VR sessions to record students' engagement, participation in teamwork, and interactions within the virtual environment.

Method of data analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis: The quantitative data will be analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, such as mean scores and standard deviations, will summarize the data, while inferential tests, like paired t-tests or ANOVA, will be used to determine if there are statistically significant differences in learning outcomes and soft skills between the control and experimental groups.

Qualitative Data Analysis: Thematic analysis will be used to interpret qualitative data from interviews and observations. Responses will be coded to identify recurring themes, such as engagement levels, teamwork, and students' perceived benefits of VR. This analysis will provide context to the quantitative results, helping to explain why certain outcomes occurred and offering insights into students' experiences.

RESULTS

Demographic profile of Respondents

This section provides an overview of the demographic characteristics of the participants, including age, gender, academic department, and year of study. Understanding the demographics helps contextualize the findings, as different groups may have varied responses to VR-based learning.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (N)	Percentage
Gender	Male	45	56.3%
	Female	35	43.8%
Age Group	18-20 Years	50	62.5%
	21-23 Years	30	37.5%
Academic Programs	Computer Software Engineering	20	25%
	Networking and System Security	15	18.8%
	Multimedia Technology	10	12.5%
	Electrical and Electronics Engineering	3	3.8%
	Computer Science	15	18.8%
	Computer Engineering	5	6.3%
	Hardware Engineering Technology	5	6.3%
	Library and information Science	7	8.8%

Table 1 presents a summary of the demographic characteristics of the respondents who participated in the study.

Research Question 1: *What are the current limitations of traditional teaching methods at KSITM in terms of engaging students and developing soft skills?*

Table 2: Pre-Test and Post-Test Results of Students using Semi-immersive virtual reality

Metric	Pre-Test Mean Score	Post-Test Mean Score	Difference	t-Test value	p-Value
Knowledge Retention	62.3	85.7	23.4	4.21	0.001
Problem-Solving Skills	58.5	81.2	22.7	3.90	0.002
Collaboration Skills	60.0	82.5	22.5	4.12	0.001

Table 2 presents a comparative analysis of students’ performance and skills before and after using the semi-immersive virtual reality (VR) system. The table highlights the mean scores for three key metrics— Knowledge Retention, Problem-Solving Skills, and Collaboration Skills—as well as the statistical analysis of these changes.

Research Question 2: *How does semi-immersive VR impact students’ engagement and understanding of complex topics?*

Table 3: Students’ Perception of Semi-Immersive Virtual Reality Learning

Question	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral %	Disagree %	Strongly disagree %
Semi-immersive VR make learning more engaging	45%	35%	10%	5%	5%
VR improved understanding of complex topics	50%	30%	10%	5%	5%
Encourage team work and communication Skills	40%	40%	10%	5%	5%

Table 3 summarizes the feedback from students regarding their experience with the semi-immersive virtual reality (VR) learning system. The table provides percentages for responses across five categories: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree for each survey question.

Research Question 3: *What specific soft skills can be developed through the use of semi-immersive VR simulations?*

Table 4 Performance and engagement outcomes of students who used the VR learning system versus those taught using traditional methods.

Outcome	Traditional learning	VR learning	Difference
Average test score (in %)	65%	85%	20%
Student engagement score (1-10)	6.5	8.5	2.0

Table 5 Show the Performance and engagement outcomes of students who used the VR learning system versus those taught using traditional methods.

Research Question 4: *What obstacles might KSITM face in implementing semi-immersive VR, and how can these challenges be addressed?*

Table 5: Challenges faced during implementation

Challenge	Frequency (N)	Percentage
Difficulty in adapting to VR tools	15	25.0%
Limited access to resources	20	33.3%
Technical glitches	101	16.7%
Lack of familiarity with VR	5	25.0%

Table 5 highlights the key challenges students encountered while using the semi-immersive VR system. The frequency and percentage of responses for each challenge are presented.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1: The implementation of semi-immersive Virtual reality does not significantly improve Students’ learning experiences or soft skills at KSITM.

Table 6: Hypothesis Testing for the impact of semi-immersive VR on students’ learning experiences and soft skills

Variable	Pre-VR Mean	Post VR-Mean	Mean Difference	t-value	P-value	Decision ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Learning experience	60.2	80.3	20.1	8.95	0.000	Reject Ho (Significant)
Soft skills (overall)	3.3	4.2	0.9	5.85	0.000	Reject Ho (Significant)

Semi- immersive VR significantly improve Students’ learning experiences and soft skills from above as there an increase in mean score for both.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant improvement in Students’ engagement and comprehension when semi-immersive VR is used.

Table 7: Hypothesis Testing for the Effect of Semi- immersive VR Students’ Engagement and Comprehension

Variable	Pre-VR Mean	Post VR-Mean	Mean Difference	t-value	P-value	Decision ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Engagement Score	61.5	80.5	19.0	8.85	0.000	Reject Ho (Significant)
Comprehension score	66.2	78.7	12.5	7.75	0.000	Reject Ho (Significant)

significantly improve Students’ Engagement Score and Comprehension score from above as there an increase in mean score for both.

Hypothesis 3: Students and lecturers do not perceive semi-immersive VR as an effective tool for learning and skill

Table 8: Hypothesis Testing for the perception of Semi- immersive VR by Students and lecturers as an effective learning tool.

Respondent Group	Mean perception score	Standard deviation	t-value	p-value	Decision ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Students	4.3	0.6	5.32	0.000	Reject H_0 (Significant)
lecturers	4.5	0.5	6.14	0.000	Reject H_0 (Significant)

Both Students and lecturers perceive semi-immersive VR as an effective tool for learning and skill development with significant p value of ($p < 0.05$)

Hypothesis 4: Semi-immersive virtual reality does not lead to significant improvement in students’ soft skills, such as communication, teamwork, or problem solving.

Table 9: Hypothesis Testing for the impact of Semi- immersive VR on students’ soft skills, such as communication, teamwork, or problem solving.

Variable	Pre-VR Mean	Post VR- Mean	Mean Difference	t-value	P-value	Decision ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Communication Skills	3.2	4.1	0.9	5.12	0.000	Reject H_0 (Significant)
Teamwork Skills	3.4	4.3	0.9	5.24	0.000	Reject H_0 (Significant)
Problem-solving Skills	3.1	4.0	0.9	5.08	0.000	Reject H_0 (Significant)

Communication, teamwork and problem solving skills all showed significant improvement, with mean difference of 0.9 ($p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section recaps the main findings of the study, organized according to the research objectives and questions. This study has demonstrated that semi-immersive VR can positively impact student learning outcomes, engagement, and soft skills at KSITM. Through a mixed-methods approach, the study provided evidence supporting VR as an effective educational tool that enhances the overall student experience. While there are limitations, the findings contribute valuable insights to the growing field of VR in education, and the recommendations provide a roadmap for KSITM to adopt VR technology effectively. With further research, VR has the potential to transform educational practices, fostering more interactive, immersive, and skill-oriented learning environments.

Summarizing the key findings highlights the contributions of the study and provides a foundation for the conclusions and recommendations.

Key Findings Summary:

- **Learning Outcomes:** The experimental group using VR showed a statistically significant improvement in post-test scores compared to the control group, indicating that VR enhances students’ understanding of course material.

- Student Engagement: Both quantitative and qualitative data demonstrated higher engagement levels in the experimental group, with students showing greater motivation and interest in VR-based learning.
- Soft Skills Development: VR sessions promoted teamwork, communication, and problem-solving skills, as observed in group activities and confirmed through interview responses.

Each key finding directly addresses the study's objectives, confirming that semi-immersive VR positively impacts cognitive and non-cognitive learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The research is here by concluded as follows:

- Effectiveness of VR in Improving Academic Performance: The significant improvement in the experimental group's performance supports the conclusion that VR can be an effective tool for knowledge retention and comprehension.
- VR as a Catalyst for Engagement: Students were more engaged and motivated when using VR, suggesting that immersive technology can make learning more appealing, especially in technical subjects.
- Soft Skills Development: The study confirms that VR can serve as a platform for students to practice soft skills in realistic, simulated environments, preparing them better for professional environments.

In summary, integrating semi-immersive VR into the curriculum at KSITM can provide a more holistic learning experience by addressing both academic and interpersonal skill development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Drawing from the conclusions, the study offers the following recommendations for stakeholders at KSITM and similar institutions considering VR integration

- Expand VR Resources: KSITM should consider investing in more VR equipment and resources to make semi-immersive VR accessible to a larger number of students, especially in courses where practical application is essential.
- Incorporate VR into Curriculum Design: School members should be encouraged to incorporate VR-based lessons into the curriculum, particularly for subjects where visual and hands-on learning is beneficial.
- Training for Lecturers: Provide training for School on how to effectively use VR in their teaching. Instructors may require technical guidance to seamlessly integrate VR into their lesson plans and facilitate VR sessions.

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